

Field-to-grid coordinate transformation for an idealised Schmidt telescope with tilted and displaced grid

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Summary

The distortion of an idealised Schmidt telescope may depend on just four physical parameters, representing a defocus and tilt/rotation of the grid. The transformations from field angles (η, ζ) to grid coordinates (G, H) are derived in terms of these parameters. It is shown that $H(\eta, \zeta)$ can be derived from measurements of $G(\eta, \zeta)$. Finally it is pointed out that the distortion polynomials are simplified if direction cosines are used to define the object direction instead of (η, ζ) .

Introduction

An ideal Schmidt telescope is distortion-free in the sense that the projection of the sky on the spherical focal surface is a perfect miniature of a portion of the celestial sphere. Although the HIPPARCOS system is far from ideal, it appears that the nominal distortion is in fact less than a milliarcsec (mas). This can be seen from Table 1 (reproduced from MAT-HIP-03567, P/L Distortion Budget, 1983 April 12). The only terms exceeding 1 mas at the corners are:

$$G = -1618607.4 \bar{\eta} + 16.7 \bar{\eta}^3 + 50.0 \bar{\eta} \bar{\zeta}^2 \quad \text{mas} \quad (1)$$

Here, $\bar{\eta} = \eta/\eta_{\max}$, $\bar{\zeta} = \zeta/\zeta_{\max}$ are normalised field angles with $\eta_{\max} = \zeta_{\max} = 0.45^\circ$. For a distortion-free system we expect however [cf. (14) below]

$$\begin{aligned} G &= -\cos \zeta \sin \eta \approx -\left(1 - \frac{1}{2} \zeta^2\right) \left(\eta - \frac{1}{6} \eta^3\right) \approx -\eta + \frac{1}{6} \eta^3 + \frac{1}{2} \eta \zeta^2 \\ &= -1620000.0 \bar{\eta} + 16.7 \bar{\eta}^3 + 50.0 \bar{\eta} \bar{\zeta}^2 \quad \text{mas} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Apart from the scale difference (origin unknown), this is in perfect agreement with the nominal distortion.

In the same document (MAT-HIP-3567, p. 11) it is stated that the most important terms of the distortion (i.e., deviation from nominal) are due to

rigid movement of the grid. This is indeed what we expect for a Schmidt system. Consequently, it would appear that the physical misalignments, as far as the optical distortion is concerned, can be represented by a small number of parameters defining the position and orientation of the grid with respect to other optical parts. This could even allow modelling the field-to-grid transformation directly in terms of such physically interpretable parameters, rather than in the form of some arbitrary polynomial.

Definition of coordinates

I shall use here only two reference frames, namely the grid frame ($\underline{o}_g$, $\underline{f}$, $\underline{g}$, $\underline{h}$) and the telescope frame ($\underline{c}_p$, $\underline{x}$, $\underline{y}$, $\underline{z}$). The unit of length is taken to be the curvature radius of the grid, which is formally equal to the focal length (1.4 m); this allows some simplification in the development, and can easily be corrected in the final results.

The grid frame ($\underline{o}_g$, $\underline{f}$, $\underline{g}$, $\underline{h}$) is identical to the grid reference frame defined in the P/L System Spec, (O_g , F , G , H). $\underline{o}_g$ is the grid centre and $\underline{f}$, $\underline{g}$, $\underline{h}$ unit vectors along which the grid coordinates (F , G , H) are measured. The position of some arbitrary point ($\underline{a}$) can be expressed in the grid system as

$$\underline{a} = \underline{o}_g + \underline{f}F + \underline{g}G + \underline{h}H \quad (3)$$

Since the curvature radius of the grid is = 1, the position of the grid curvature centre is

$$\underline{c}_g = \underline{o}_g + \underline{f} \quad (4)$$

The telescope frame ($\underline{c}_p$, $\underline{x}$, $\underline{y}$, $\underline{z}$) is very similar to the primary P/L reference frame (O_p , X_p , Y_p , Z_p) defined by MATRA; they are in fact identical for the nominal instrument. For the present purpose it is however inconvenient to use the beam combiner as the only reference part. Although a Schmidt system ideally has no optical axis, it does have a single point of symmetry, viz. the curvature centre of the primary mirror, $\underline{c}_p$. It is natural to take this as origin for the telescope frame, and to choose the optical axis direction ($\underline{x}$) merely for convenience. Thus, we take $\underline{x}$ to be the unit vector in the direction from $\underline{o}_g$ to $\underline{c}_p$, $\underline{z}$ to be in the plane spanned

by $\underline{x}$ and Z_p (i.e., as closely parallel to Z_p as possible), and finally $\underline{y} = \underline{z} \times \underline{x}$ to complete the right-handed triad.

After reflection by the beam combiner, the direction to an object is given by the unit vector $\underline{u}$. Field angles (η, ζ) are here defined directly in terms of the direction cosines with respect to $[\underline{x} \ \underline{y} \ \underline{z}]$, so that really they do not constitute a separate reference frame:

$$\begin{aligned}\underline{x}'\underline{u} &= u_x = \cos \zeta \cos \eta \\ \underline{y}'\underline{u} &= u_y = \cos \zeta \sin \eta \\ \underline{z}'\underline{u} &= u_z = \sin \zeta\end{aligned}\tag{5}$$

This definition of field angles is practically identical to MATRA's, in that the origin ($\eta = \zeta = 0$) corresponds to the grid centre ($\underline{o}_g$ or O_g) in both viewing directions, and that $\eta = \text{const}$ along meridional great circles.

Misalignment parameters

Since the grid centre ($\underline{o}_g$) by definition is on the $\underline{x}$ axis, there are in fact only four free parameters for the location and orientation of the grid, viz. the defocus (Δx , in units of the grid curvature radius!) and three rotation angles ϕ, θ, ψ . All four parameters are typically of the order of 10^{-3} or less, and equal to zero for the nominal instrument. The grid frame ($\underline{o}_g, \underline{f}, \underline{g}, \underline{h}$) is obtained from the telescope frame ($\underline{c}_p, \underline{x}, \underline{y}, \underline{z}$) by the following operations:

- (i) a translation of origin along $\underline{x}$ by $\Delta x - 1$;
- (ii) a rotation about the third axis by ψ ;
- (iii) a rotation about the second axis by θ ;
- (iv) a rotation about the first axis by ϕ .

The directional triads are therefore related by the transformation

$$\begin{aligned}[\underline{f} \ \underline{g} \ \underline{h}] &= [\underline{x} \ \underline{y} \ \underline{z}] \underline{A}_3(\psi) \underline{A}_2(\theta) \underline{A}_1(\phi) \\ &= [\underline{x} \ \underline{y} \ \underline{z}] \underline{A}\end{aligned}\tag{6}$$

where $\underline{A}_i(q)$ signifies a rotation by the angle q about the i :th axis of the preceding triad. The full rotation matrix is

$$\underline{A} = \begin{bmatrix} c\theta \ c\psi & s\phi \ s\theta \ c\psi - c\phi \ s\psi & c\phi \ s\theta \ c\psi + s\phi \ s\psi \\ c\theta \ s\psi & s\phi \ s\theta \ s\psi + c\phi \ c\psi & c\phi \ s\theta \ s\psi - s\phi \ c\psi \\ -s\theta & s\phi \ c\theta & c\phi \ c\theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

with $s = \sin$, $c = \cos$.

For any point $\underline{a}$, the grid coordinates (F, G, H) can be calculated from the telescope coordinates (X, Y, Z) by means of

$$\begin{bmatrix} F \\ G \\ H \end{bmatrix} = \underline{A}' \begin{bmatrix} X + 1 - \Delta x \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where $\underline{A}'$ is the transpose (= inverse) of $\underline{A}$.

Exact field-to-grid transformation

For any object direction $\underline{u}$, the principal ray can be written in parametric form, $\underline{c}_p = \underline{u}t$. Its intersection with the grid can be determined from the condition that it is at unit distance from the grid curvature centre, $\underline{c}_g$. Introducing the small displacement vector

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{d} &= \underline{c}_g - \underline{c}_p \\ &= \underline{f} - \underline{x}(1 - \Delta x) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

we have the quadratic equation in t ,

$$|\underline{u}t + \underline{d}|^2 = 1 \quad (10)$$

from which

$$t = [1 + (\underline{u}'\underline{d})^2 - \underline{d}'\underline{d}]^{\frac{1}{2}} - \underline{u}'\underline{d} \quad (11)$$

Using the component forms of $\underline{u}$ and $\underline{d}$, eqn (5) and

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{x}'\underline{d} &= d_x = \cos \theta \cos \psi - 1 + \Delta x \\ \underline{y}'\underline{d} &= d_y = \cos \theta \sin \psi \\ \underline{z}'\underline{d} &= d_z = -\sin \theta \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

we calculate t from (11) and obtain the grid coordinates by means of (8), i.e.

$$\begin{bmatrix} F \\ G \\ H \end{bmatrix} = \underline{A}' \begin{bmatrix} -u_x t + 1 - \Delta x \\ -u_y t \\ -u_z t \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

Exact transformation for the nominal instrument

With $\Delta x = \phi = \theta = \psi = 0$ we have from (12), $\underline{d} = \underline{0}$ and from (11), $t = 1$; finally (7) and (13) yield

$$\begin{aligned} F &= 1 - u_x = 1 - \cos \zeta \cos \eta \simeq \frac{1}{2}(\eta^2 + \zeta^2) + \dots \\ G &= -u_y = -\cos \zeta \sin \eta \simeq -\eta + \frac{1}{6}\eta^3 + \frac{1}{2}\eta\zeta^2 + \dots \\ H &= -u_z = -\sin \zeta \simeq -\zeta + \frac{1}{6}\zeta^3 + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

It can be noted that (u_y, u_z) would be a more natural representation of the object direction [with $u_x = (1 - u_y^2 - u_z^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ implied] than the field angles (η, ζ) . This is in fact utilized in the following.

Polynomial expansions

Considering that u_y, u_z are of the order of 10^{-2} and $\Delta x, \phi, \theta, \psi$ even smaller, it is reasonable to expand G and H in polynomials up to third order in these quantities (since fourth-order terms would be less than 10^{-8} rad $\simeq 2$ mas). Thus, eqns (5) and (12) yield

$$\begin{aligned} u_x &= 1 - \frac{1}{2}(u_y^2 + u_z^2), & d_x &= \Delta x - \frac{1}{2}(\theta^2 + \psi^2) \\ u_y &= u_y & d_y &= \psi - \frac{1}{6}\psi^3 - \frac{1}{2}\psi\theta^2 \\ u_z &= u_z & d_z &= -\theta + \frac{1}{6}\theta^3 \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

and by insertion into (11),

$$t = (1 - \Delta x)(1 - \psi u_y + \theta u_z) + \frac{1}{2}\Delta x(u_y^2 + u_z^2) \quad (16)$$

Since $\underline{A}'$ in (13) is multiplied by quantities of the order of u_y, u_z , it is sufficient to expand the elements of $\underline{A}$ to second order in the orientation

angles. The final equations are, after multiplication by the curvature radius of the grid (R),

$$G(u_y, u_z) = -R(1 - \Delta x - \frac{1}{2}\phi^2 + \frac{1}{2}\psi^2)u_y + R[\theta\psi - (1 - \Delta x)\phi]u_z + \frac{1}{2}R\psi u_y^2 - R\theta u_y u_z - \frac{1}{2}R\psi u_z^2 \quad (17)$$

$$H(u_y, u_z) = -R(1 - \Delta x - \frac{1}{2}\phi^2 + \frac{1}{2}\theta^2)u_z + R(1 - \Delta x)\phi u_y + \frac{1}{2}R\theta u_y^2 + R\psi u_y u_z - \frac{1}{2}R\theta u_z^2 \quad (18)$$

[Numerical comparison with the exact formulae (9)-(13) showed an rms error below 0.1 mas over a field of $\pm 50'$ in both field angles, assuming the misalignment parameters $\Delta x = 0.00001$ (14 μm), $\phi = 0.0003$, $\theta = -0.0008$, $\psi = 0.0005$.]

Introducing $P = (1 - \Delta x - \frac{1}{2}\phi^2)R$ we have to the same order of accuracy the simpler expressions

$$G = -P(1 + \frac{1}{2}\psi^2)u_y - P(\phi - \theta\psi)u_z + \frac{1}{2}P\psi u_y^2 - P\theta u_y u_z - \frac{1}{2}P\psi u_z^2 \quad (19)$$

$$H = -P(1 + \frac{1}{2}\theta^2)u_z + P\phi u_y + \frac{1}{2}P\theta u_y^2 - P\psi u_y u_z - \frac{1}{2}P\theta u_z^2 \quad (20)$$

If $G(u_y, u_z)$ is measured, and we have a provisional value for P , we will be able to calculate θ and ψ from the second-order terms, whereupon the first-order terms give ϕ and an improved P . From the parameters P , ϕ , θ , and ψ we can then calculate the transformation $H(u_y, u_z)$, if required.

It is also interesting to note that (19)-(20) contain no third-order terms in u_y or u_z . If we express the transformations in terms of η , ζ by substituting u_y, u_z as in (14), we find

$$G = -P(1 + \frac{1}{2}\psi^2)\eta - P(\phi - \theta\psi)\zeta + \frac{1}{2}P\psi\eta^2 - P\theta\eta\zeta - \frac{1}{2}P\psi\zeta^2 + \frac{1}{6}P\eta^3 + \frac{1}{2}P\eta\zeta^2 \quad (21)$$

$$H = -P(1 + \frac{1}{2}\theta^2)\zeta + P\phi\eta + \frac{1}{2}P\theta\eta^2 - P\psi\eta\zeta - \frac{1}{2}P\theta\zeta^2 + \frac{1}{6}P\zeta^3 \quad (22)$$

From this it can be concluded that the third-order terms should be constant, and that the variations of the two terms η^2 and ζ^2 should be equal and opposite.

FIGURE 1. Definition of telescope frame ($c_p, \underline{x}, \underline{y}, \underline{z}$) and grid frame ($o_g, \underline{f}, \underline{g}, \underline{h}$). $\underline{u}$ = object direction, c_p = centre of curvature of primary mirror, c_g = centre of curvature of grid, o_g = centre of grid

MATRA ESPACE
HIPPARCOS

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G_{iN} (in "grid" mas) =	+	.015	
	-	1618607.400	
	-	.368	
η and ξ are field angle	+	.004	
positions normalized to 1	+	.011	
at the field extremities ; for	-	.009	
$\omega_0 = 0.45^\circ$ and $\xi_0 = 0.45^\circ$	+	16.700	
it corresponds $\eta = 1$ and $\xi = 1$	-	.023	
	+	50.010	
1 "grid"mas = 6.8 nanometer	-	0.041	

ω^2
 ω^2
 ω^2
 ω^2
 ω^3
 ω^2
 ω^2
 ω^3

TABLE 1 - NOMINAL DISTORTION